

Predatory Potential of *Coccinella septempunctata* Adults Sex on *Lipaphis erysimi* and *Aphis nerii*

Muhammad Hanif Buriro¹, Lubna Bashir Rajput¹, Arfan Ahmed Gilal^{1*}, Muhammad Musavir Koondhar¹, Ghulam Hussain Jatoi², Sajjad Hussain Rind³, Fatima Nizamani¹, Muhammad Hamza Iftikhar¹, Yahya Khan Mari¹, Ramsha Mazhar¹ and Muhammad Naem Qureshi¹

1. Department of Entomology, Faculty of Crop Protection, Sindh Agriculture University, Tandojam, Pakistan
2. Department of Plant Pathology, Faculty of Crop Protection, Sindh Agriculture University, Tandojam, Pakistan
3. Agriculture Research Sindh, Tandojam, Pakistan

*Corresponding author e-mail: aagilal@sau.edu.pk

SUMMARY

Coccinella septempunctata is the most important biocontrol agent that prey on a wide variety of insect pests, especially aphids which cause 9–96% losses in crop yields. Therefore, a laboratory study was carried out on the functional response of *C. septempunctata* adults (males, females, and combined males plus female) on two aphid species i.e., *Lipaphis erysimi* and *Aphis nerii*. Three densities, i.e., 50, 75, and 100 of both species were provided separately to all three treatments of *C. septempunctata*. Each prey density was provided to the adult treatments in separate petri dishes (9 cm) and replenished on daily basis till the conversion of individual instar into the next stage. The observation was recorded on searching ability, handling time, and feeding potential of *C. septempunctata* adults till their death. It was observed that maximum consumption rate of adults (male, female and combination of both) of *C. septempunctata* was recorded when both aphid species were offered at 100 aphids density, followed by seventy-five and fifty aphid densities. Among adults, *C. septempunctata* female showed relatively more preference on both the aphid species that was not significantly different from mean consumption of males, whereas the least consumption of both the aphid species was observed when they were offered to the combination of males and females. Among the two species, adults showed more preference for *A. nerii* than *L. erysimi*. Both males and females showed lowest searching rate on *A. nerii* than *L. erysimi*. Moreover, both females and males showed lower handling time and maximum predation of *L. erysimi*. It has been also observed that predation efficiency of all the adult's combination showed a declining trend with the increasing prey density, thus exhibiting type II function response. Therefore, it is suggested that conservation strategies should be carried out for *C. septempunctata* to get maximum population regulation of various aphid species including *L. erysimi* and *A. nerii*.

Keywords: Aphids, Coccinellidae, Biological control, Pests, Predation

INTRODUCTION

Coccinellids are members of the family Coccinellidae and are amongst the most familiar beetles known variously as ladybirds (Michaud, 2012). Several coccinellids species are powerful predators and mostly prey on many soft body and scale insects of order Hemiptera as well as order Thysanoptera and many mite species which included in order Acarina around the world (Slipinski, 2013). Seven spotted beetle, *Coccinella*

septempunctata L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) also called aphids lion, because it mainly preys on many aphid species (Honek et al., 2013).

Aphids are one of the most destructive insect pests and is distributed all over the world (Fondren et al., 2004; Hassan et al., 2023). The aphids also act as vectors for numerous plant viruses (Bilashini et al., 2007; Bilashini & Singh, 2009). Almost 5,000 species of Aphididae have been recognized, from which 450 are recorded from crop plants (Blackman & Eastop, 2000; Favret, 2000). Mustard aphid (*Lipaphis erysimi*), and milkweed aphid (*Aphis nerii*) are economically most important aphid species and in Pakistan, their population was found abundantly (Mushtaq et al., 2013). The control of aphids, mostly rely on the use of synthetic insecticides (Messelink et al., 2013). These insecticides are mostly successful to suppress pest population and provide quick relief. However, the use of these hazardous chemicals, create severe problems such as target pests become resistance to chemicals, sudden pest resurgence, quickly outbreaks of secondary pests, disturbing or destroying non target species, increasing susceptibility of crops, adverse effects on environment, bioaccumulation and health hazard to humans and cattle due environmental and ecological concerns, thus there is a urgent need to developed alternative insect control methods (Khan et al., 2015, 2016; Sattar et al., 2018).

Coccinellidae, or ladybeetles are an important part of the biotope in various climatic zones (Khan et al., 2007; Uygun & Karabüyük, 2013). Most family members are predators and play an important role in regulating the number of plant pests (Sattar et al., 2018). Beetles destroy aphids, leaflets, shields, thrips, ticks and other small arthropods, as well as scallops on the stage of eggs. Seven spotted lady beetle is a multicultural with broad dispersion abilities (Ali & Rizvi, 2009). It mainly feeds on large number of aphids (Doddamani et al., 2017). Aphids feed on host plants and damage it in several ways such as they curl after aphids attack the leaves of host plant curled and deformed, and plant shoots are stunted as well as they also affect host plants as introduce plant viruses (Raboudi et al., 2002). Both larvae and adults of seven spotted lady beetles are highly active predators and are extremely polyphagous in nature (Yu et al., 2014). As compared to other coccinellids, (*Brumoides suturalis*, *Cheilomenes sexmaculata*, *Menochilus sexmaculatus*), the population of seven spotted beetle, consumed more aphids (Soni et al., 2013). This is the reason behind that *C. septempunctata* has often been introduced in new countries as part of classical biological control programs and considered for biological control (Michaud, 2012).

The peak population period of beetle's population is the start of spring until the cool sets in drop. When the temperature is going to decrease, the beetles searched for protected sites for hibernation (Mayo, 1998). Although coccinellids are not directly dangerous to humans by biting or stinging them, but they may produce unpleasant smells or make unpleasant taste because of the juicy material secreted from their legs for their defense purpose. The beetle "play dead" during in risk since many different super predators will not prey an insect that doesn't move (Fleming, 2000; Marshall, 2001). Seven spotted beetles occupy relatively incredible status among the different naturally occurring biological control agents. Many scientists in different parts of the world have conducted research on the behavior and efficiency of beetle predation in field and under the laboratory environment with varying results. This predator feed on other living

organisms; the immature and mature beetles feed on various types of insects which damage the crops, especially sucking insect pests (Anonymous, 1997).

Integrated pest management system is a broad methodology to control pest population below the economic injury level by using other living organisms known as natural enemies or biological control agents (Solangi, 2004; Ehler, 2006; Nizamani et al., 2020; Sepe et al., 2020). This program can decrease the use of hazardous chemical insecticides that are applied to manage many insect pests. Moreover, coccinellids beetles have been successfully organized in various integrated management programs and biological control programs against many insect pests on different crops (Ahmed et al., 2016). Biological control agents (Coccinellids) consist of an important component of various incorporated insect pest management programs, but various chemical insecticides affect their performance (Yu et al., 2014; Skouras et al., 2017). Therefore, considering the importance of *C. septempunctata* against aphids, the study was conducted to determine the handling rate, search rate and host preference of *Coccinella septempunctata* adult on *A. nerii* and *L. erysimi* under laboratory conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Place of work

The experiment was conducted at the Stored Grain Pest Research Laboratory, Department of Entomology, Faculty of Crop Protection, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam, Sindh, Pakistan.

Collection and rearing of *Coccinella septempunctata* and aphid species

Coccinella septempunctata adults were collected from surrounding mustard fields of Tandojam and reared on *L. erysimi* and *A. nerii* respectively under laboratory conditions of $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $60 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity. Freshly emerged F1 generation larvae were used in study. The collected larvae and adults were kept in collecting jars and brought to entomology laboratory for rearing. Adult males and females were allowed to mate in cages (1 square feet) covered with wooden hardboard and provided with plenty of food in the form of infested twigs of aphids along with small droplets of honey solution on a piece of wet cotton wool for their continuous food supply. In order to avoid contamination, after 24 hours dry twigs were replaced with fresh aphid infested twigs. For oviposition of *C. septempunctata*, tissue paper and butter papers were placed inside the cage. Females laid eggs on tissue paper and the walls of cages these eggs were removed with the help of camel hairbrush then counted and transferred in Petri dishes (9 cm diameter). The newly emerged adults were used for the study.

The culture of *A. nerii* and *L. erysimi* was maintained at the brassica and nerum plants at the Institute of Plant Protection, Agriculture Research, Sindh Tandojam. Freshly emerged aphids were used in the study.

Experimental setup, data collection and analysis

The experiment was set in Complete Randomize Design (CRD) with three treatments and three replications. The following treatments were used in the study:

T1 = Males

T2 = Females

T3 = Combined males and females

To determine the feeding efficiency of adult male, female along with combination of both males and females in pair, they were offered three prey densities i.e., 50, 75, and 100 of the two aphid species i.e., *Lipaphis erysimi* and *Aphis nerii*. Each prey density was offered to the individual treatment inside the separate petri dishes.

Data was collected for the number of prey species consumed on daily basis by counting the number of aphids left out after twenty-four hours. Fresh densities of both the aphid species were provided to individual adult treatment of *C. septempunctata* on daily basis till they died.

Experiment was organized according to completely randomized design as three replications were maintained for each treatment (larvae).

Following functional response parameters will be calculated using the following formulae by plotting the number of preys consumed versus individual prey density.

$$\text{Searching ability } = a' = a/T_t$$

$$\text{Handling Time} = T_h = b/a'$$

$$\text{Maximum predation rate} = 1/T_h$$

Where a' = instantaneous rate of discovery / catch

a = the intercept of the linear regression line (catching frequency versus prey density)

T_t = exposure time (here it is assumed as 24-hours because data is collected on daily basis)

T_h = handling time (hours per prey individual consumed) that is time to catch and consume the prey = b/a' , where b is the slope of the linear regression line

Feeding potential data was analysed using ANOVA (Analysis of Variance), whereas LSD (Least Significant Difference) test was used for mean comparison having significant difference. All analysis was done using STATISTIX 8.3 computer software.

RESULTS

Feeding potential of male *Coccinella septempunctata* on *Aphis nerii* and *Lipaphis erysimi*

Figure 1 showed the results regarding the feeding potential of male *C. septempunctata* on various densities of *A. nerii* and *L. erysimi* under laboratory conditions. The results of study confirmed a significant ($F = 11.00$, $P < 0.001$) difference in the feeding potential of male *C. septempunctata* on *L. erysimi* and *A. nerii*. Moreover, results also confirmed a significant impact of the various prey densities of both the species on the predatory potential of the male *C. septempunctata* ($F = 317.15$, $P < 0.001$) along with interaction analysis of aphid species and their densities also exhibited a significant impact on male's feeding potential ($F = 13.45$, $P < 0.001$). A rise in the predatory efficiency of the male *C. septempunctata* was noticed when it was provided with the increasing prey densities of both the species as it showed relatively more preference for *A. nerii* than *L. erysimi*. According to results, the maximum predation of male *C. septempunctata* (60.81 ± 2.40 aphids per day) was recorded when it was provided with hundred prey density of *L. erysimi*, followed by hundred aphid density of *A. nerii* (56.33 ± 2.73 aphids per day). The minimum mean consumption of male *C. septempunctata* was recorded on fifty prey density of *L. erysimi* (17.84 ± 1.54 aphids per day), followed by 27.47 ± 1.38 aphids per day consumption recorded on fifty prey

density of *A. nerii*. The mean predatory potential of male *C. septempunctata* on seventy-five densities of *L. erysimi* and *A. nerii* was observed as 37.01 ± 2.17 and 43.45 ± 1.86 aphids per day, respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Feeding potential of adult male *Coccinella septempunctata* on aphid species at different prey densities

*Means followed by same letters are not significantly different from each other (LSD = 2.0171, $P < 0.05$)

1. Feeding potential of female *Coccinella septempunctata* on *Aphis nerii* and *Lipahis erysimi*

Figure 2 showed the results regarding the feeding potential of female *C. septempunctata* on various densities of *A. nerii* and *L. erysimi* under laboratory conditions. The results of study confirmed a significant ($F = 39.49$, $P < 0.001$) difference in the feeding potential of female *C. septempunctata* on *L. erysimi* and *A. nerii*. Moreover, results also confirmed a significant impact of the various prey densities of both the species on the predatory potential of the female *C. septempunctata* ($F = 382.06$, $P < 0.001$) along with interaction analysis of aphid species and their densities also exhibited a significant impact on female's feeding potential ($F = 3.67$, $P = 0.0267$). A rise in the predatory efficiency of the female *C. septempunctata* was noticed when it was provided with the increasing prey densities of both the species as it showed relatively more preference for *A. nerii* than *L. erysimi*.

Figure 2: Feeding potential of adult female *Coccinella septempunctata* on aphid species at different prey densities; Means followed by same letters are not significantly different from each other (LSD = 1.8210, $P < 0.05$).

Feeding potential of male and female (combined) *Coccinella septempunctata* on *Aphis neri* and *Lipahis erysimi*

Figure 3 showed the results regarding the feeding potential of male and female *C. septempunctata* (combined) on various densities of *A. neri* and *L. erysimi* under laboratory conditions. The results of study confirmed a highly significant ($F = 35.39$, $P < 0.001$) difference in the feeding potential of combined male and female *C. septempunctata* on *L. erysimi* and *A. neri*. Results also confirmed a highly significant impact of the various prey densities of both the species on the predatory potential of the combined male and female *C. septempunctata* ($F = 251.18$, $P < 0.001$) along with interaction analysis of aphid species and their densities also exhibited a significant impact on their feeding potential ($F = 16.95$, $P < 0.001$). A rise in the predatory efficiency of the female *C. septempunctata* was noticed when it was provided with the increasing prey densities of both the species as it showed relatively more preference for *A. neri* than *L. erysimi*. According to results, the maximum predation of combined male and female *C. septempunctata* (45.49 ± 2.30 aphids per day) was recorded when it was provided with hundred prey density of *A. neri*, followed by feeding on hundred aphid density of *L. erysimi* (33.35 ± 3.44 aphids). The minimum mean consumption of combined male and female *C. septempunctata* was recorded on fifty prey density of *L. erysimi* (15.63 ± 1.71 aphids per day), followed by 15.97 ± 1.36 aphids per day consumption recorded on fifty prey density of *A. neri*. The mean predatory potential of combined male and female *C. septempunctata* on seventy-five density of *L. erysimi*

and *A. nerii* was observed as 28.85 ± 2.60 and 31.85 ± 1.73 aphids per day, respectively (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Feeding potential of adult male and female (combined) *Coccinella septempunctata* on aphid species at different prey densities; *Means followed by same letters are not significantly different from each other (LSD = 1.223, P < 0.05).

Search rate, handling time and predation of *Coccinella septempunctata* adults on aphid species

Male Coccinella septempunctata

The data presented in Table 1 show the search rate, handling time (in hours), maximum predation and (R^2) of male *C. septempunctata* on aphid species i.e., *L. erysimi* and *Aphis nerii*. The results revealed that search rate of male *C. septempunctata* was comparatively lower on *A. nerii* (0.0367 hours) than *L. erysimi* (1.079 hours), however, it took relatively lower handling time (0.795 hours) to prey on *L. erysimi*, whereas it took 15.70 hours handling time to predate on *A. nerii*. Accordingly, the maximum predation rate (1.256) of male *C. septempunctata* was recorded on *L. erysimi* than *A. nerii* (0.0637). Moreover, co-efficient of determination (R^2) values of male *C. septempunctata* was moderate on both the aphid species with relatively more on *L. erysimi* (0.4916) that indicated that all above mentioned parameters are relatively more defined by its prey density than *A. nerii* with R^2 value of 0.3046.

Female Coccinella septempunctata

The data recorded in Table 1 also illustrated the maximum predation rate, search rate, handling time and (R^2) of female *C. septempunctata* on two different aphid species i.e.,

A. nerii and *L. erysimi*. According to results of study the maximum predation of females (0.997) was recorded on *L. erysimi* as compared to *A. nerii* (0.224). Furthermore, the searching efficiency of female *C. septempunctata* was recorded lower on *A. nerii* (0.146) than *L. erysimi* (0.765). Results also indicated that female *C. septempunctata* needed lower handling time (1.002 hours) on *L. erysimi* as compared to *A. nerii* (4.465 hours). Besides this the co-efficient value (0.4482) recorded on *L. erysimi* by females was comparatively higher than the value recorded *A. nerii* (0.3442) that indicated that prey density of *L. erysimi* was more determinant in the feeding potential of female *C. septempunctata*.

Male and female *Coccinella septempunctata* (combined)

Table 1 also shows the results regarding handling time, search rate, maximum predation rate and R^2 of combined male and female *C. septempunctata* on *L. erysimi* and *A. nerii*. Findings of study revealed that combined feeding of both male and female *C. septempunctata* required lowest handling time (1.075 hours) on *A. nerii* while it took highest handling time (3.315 hours) on *L. erysimi*. However, the maximum predation rate was recorded (0.930) on *A. nerii* than *L. erysimi* (0.301). Furthermore, according to results the minimum (0.7026) searching efficiency of combined male and female was observed on *L. erysimi* and maximum (0.548) on *A. nerii*. The results regarding to co-efficient determination (R^2) value of 0.3363 for combined male and female *C. septempunctata* on *A. nerii* shows that all above mentioned parameters are relatively more defined by its prey density than R^2 value of 0.0889 calculated for *L. erysimi*.

Table 1: Search rate, handling time and predation rate of *Coccinella septempunctata* adults on aphid species *Lipaphis erysimi* and *Aphis nerii*.

Parameter	Male		Female		Male + Female	
	<i>L. erysimi</i>	<i>A. nerii</i>	<i>L. erysimi</i>	<i>A. nerii</i>	<i>L. erysimi</i>	<i>A. nerii</i>
Search rate (hours)	1.079	0.0367	0.765	0.146	0.026	0.548
Handling time (hours)	0.795	15.7	1.002	4.465	3.315	1.075
Maximum predation	1.256	0.0637	0.997	0.224	0.301	0.93
R^2	0.4916	0.3046	0.4482	0.3442	0.0889	0.3363

DISCUSSION

Studies on functional response of *C. septempunctata* L. adults (male, female along with combination of males and females) on different aphid species were carried out under laboratory conditions. Three different densities i.e., 50, 75 and 100 of two aphid species *L. erysimi* and *A. nerii* were offered to different combination of adults of *C. septempunctata*. The results on feeding potential of different treatments of adult *C. septempunctata* as mentioned above confirmed a significant impact of aphid species and their densities on the feeding potential of adult *C. septempunctata*. According to findings of the study, females were found to be comparatively more voracious, but not significantly different from males, but relatively more than combination of both males and females. Moreover, predatory potential of male, females and their combination

(male plus females) showed increasing trend with increasing densities of their prey i.e., *L. erysimi* and *A. nerii*. Thus, the maximum number of *A. nerii* and *L. erysimi* were consumed by female *C. septempunctata* (62.96 ± 2.77 and 58.28 ± 2.38 aphids per day, respectively when both prey species were offered to them at density of hundred aphids per day. Male and combined feeding of both males and females also showed their preference towards *A. nerii* than *L. erysimi* at almost all the densities of their host aphid species.

Many previous studies also confirmed the predatory potential of *C. septempunctata* on various aphid species, where fourth larval instar and females are found to be more voracious on them. Studies of Marri et al. (2021) on predatory potential of males and female adults of *C. septempunctata* on the two aphid species *Brassica campestris* L. and *Calotropis procera* L. indicated that females were found to be more voracious than males as both showed more preference for *B. campestris* than *C. procera*. Findings of Darwish (2019) also supported our outcome as their experiments on the predation efficiency and feeding preference of *C. septempunctata* and *C. undecimpunctata* showed their consumption of both the species increased with their developing instars as 4th instar of both species was more aggressive on the prey offered i.e., *Myzus persicae*, *Rhopalosiphum padi* and *Aphis gossypii*.

The comparatively more feeding potential of female *C. septempunctata* than their corresponding males or their combinations on various densities of *A. nerii* and *L. erysimi* may be because of their more energy requirement for the reproduction capabilities i.e., mating, fertilization and oviposition. Similar to our studies, Hamid et al. (2021) also confirmed that female *C. septempunctata* were found to be more voracious on different aphid species i.e., *L. erysimi*, *Diuraphis noxia* Kurjumov, and *A. nerii*, followed by 4th instar larvae and males. Previous studies also found that due to the more requirement of energy by the fourth instar to become pupae and then adults, whereas reproduction need for female required them to feed more on their prey (Khan & Yoldaş, 2018; Srivastava, 2003; Xue et al., 2009).

Findings of this study on search rate, handling time and predation of *C. septempunctata* adults on *A. nerii* and *L. erysimi* revealed that among different adults' treatments, lowest searching efficiency was recorded for combination of males and females on *L. erysimi*, followed by males on *A. nerii*. Moreover, lowest searching efficiency of females was recorded on *A. nerii* than *L. erysimi*. Thus, both males and females showed lowest searching rate on *A. nerii* than *L. erysimi*. Moreover, both females and males showed lower handling time and maximum predation of *L. erysimi*. It has been also observed that predation efficiency of all the adult's combination showed a declining trend with the increasing prey density, thus exhibiting type II function response.

It has been reported that most of the insect predators exhibited type-II functional response where they initially feed more prey when prey density is increased, however then tapered off later as no effect of increasing prey density is observed on their feeding, because most of the time is consumed in handling and consuming the prey (Holling, 1959). Therefore, similar types of results have been observed in our study especially when *A. nerii* is offered as prey to *C. septempunctata*. Similar type of results was also reported by Omkar and Srivastava and Omkar (2003) while studying the predation and searching efficiency of *C. septempunctata*. They observed that prey handling time of

the fourth instar decreased from 31.03 to 4.97min as the prey density increased from 50 to 800. Moreover, the number of preys consumed by predatory stages initially increased rapidly with increase in prey density but slow down with further increase in prey density, thus, exhibiting type II functional response. The reasons behind the more consumption of predators when their prey populations are higher may be due to the reasons that found more interaction with their prey along with time to handle prey with minimum searching time because of smaller area and the level of starvation.

Similar types of results were also reported for different predator coccinellid species. While studying the predation rate of *C. septempunctata*, *C. sexmaculata* and *H. variegata* for *S. graminum*, *A. maidis*, *M. miscanthi* and *E. kerri* at different prey densities, Omkar et al. (2005) observed in their studies that adult beetles of *C. septempunctata* are also voracious feeders of aphids as their daily consumption rate was observed between 28 - 33.2 aphids per day when aphids were provided at density of fifty aphids, but no significant variation between days. However, larvae were found to be more fed on aphids that may be because of their more nutritional requirement for future development till pupal and adults' growth. Therefore, as compared to adults, larvae may be more preferred for the biological control of pests because of their more voraciousness. Similar suggestions have also been made earlier by Khan and Suhail (2001), and Pervez and Omkar (2005). The lower feeding of the adults and larvae of *C. septempunctata* at higher densities of prey may be because they become satiated, thus, it may be concluded that coccinellids showed more effective results at lower densities of their prey (Mills, 1982).

It has been also found in variable studies on predatory potential of different life stages of *C. septempunctata* that handling time for all of its life stages varied for three different species i.e., *L. erysimi*, *D. noxia*, and *A. neri* under observations. The handling time showed an increasing trend with growth stage of the beetle as first instar was showed lowest handling, whereas it was highest for fourth instar and females. Similar type of results was also reported in earlier works on *C. septempunctata* against *A. pisum* (Khan and Yoldaş, 2018; Omkar & Srivastava, 2003). It has been observed that handling time generally showed a great variation depending upon the developmental stage and species under observation, for both predator and prey (Veeravel & Baskaran, 1997; Xia et al., 2003) as at the lower densities of aphids, it become difficult for the predator to find their prey items as they spread out more widely, hence become difficult for predator to search them and capturing them (Hodek, 1967).

CONCLUSIONS

It was concluded that maximum consumption rate of adults *C. septempunctata* was recorded at hundred densities of *L. erysimi* and *A. neri*, followed by seventy-five and fifty densities. Among adult *C. septempunctata*, female showed relatively more preference on both the aphid species, but not significantly different from mean consumption of males. Among the two species, adults showed more preference for *A. neri* than *L. erysimi*. Both males and females showed lowest searching rate on *A. neri* than *L. erysimi*, whereas lower handling time and maximum predation was recorded on *L. erysimi*. The predation efficiency of all the adult's combination showed a declining trend with the increasing prey density, thus exhibiting type II function response. Therefore, it is suggested that *C. septempunctata* population should be conserved in

field conditions to manage population of aphid species particularly *L. erysimi* to reduce their losses to get maximum yields.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, K. S., Majeed, A. M., Haidary, A. A., & Haider, N. (2016). Integrated pest management tactics and predatory coccinellids: A review. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 4(1), 591-600.
- Ali, A., & Rizvi, P. Q. (2009). Life table studies of *Menochilus sexmaculatus* Fabr. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) at varying temperature on *Lipaphis erysimi* Kalt. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 7(7), 897-901.
- Anonymous. (1997). Ladybird beetle: in ed., Microsoft Encarta Encyclopedia. Houghton Mifflin Company, 97.
- Bilashini, Y., & Singh, T. K., (2009). Studies on population dynamics and feeding potential of *Coccinella septempunctata* Linnaeus in relation to *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kaltenbach) on cabbage. *Indian Journal of Applied Entomology*, 23, 99-103.
- Bilashini, Y., Singh, T. K., & Singh, R. K. R. (2007). Biological control potential of *Coccinella septempunctata* Linnaeus (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) on major homopteran pests of rapeseed. *Journal of biological Control*, 2, 157-162.
- Blackman, R. L., & Eastop, V. F. (2000). Aphids on the world's crops: An identification and information guide (2nd ed.). John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Darwish, A. A. E. (2019). The predation efficiency and feeding preference of *Coccinella septempunctata* L. and *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) on some prey species. *Menoufia Journal of Plant Protection*, 4(1), 7-16.
- Doddamani, V. B. Behere, G. T., Firake, D. M., & Nongkynrih, B. (2017). Biology of *Coccinella septempunctata* on mustard aphid *Lipaphis erysimi*. *Indian Journal of Hill Farming*, 30(1), 41-44.
- Ehler, L. E. (2006). Integrated pest management (IPM): definition, historical development and implementation, and the other IPM. *Journal of Pest Management Sciences* 62(9), 787-789.
- Favret, C. R. (2000). Migratory aphid habitat selection in agricultural and adjacent natural habitats. University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign.
- Fleming, R. (2000). Entomology notes #6: Lady beetles. University of Michigan Museum of Zoology. Retrieved February 28, 2000, from <http://insects.ummz.lsa.umich.edu/MES/notes/entnotes6.html>
- Fondren, K. M., McCullough, D. G., & Walter, A. J. (2004). Insect predators and augmentative biological control of balsam twig aphid (*Mindarus abietinus* Koch) (Homoptera: Aphididae) on christmas tree plantations. *Environmental Entomology*, 33, 1652-1661.
- Hamid, M. F., Hameed, Y., Sarmad, M., Abbas, K., Shahzaib, M., Zakria, M., & Zaka, S. M. (2021). Functional response of *Coccinella septempunctata* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) to different species of aphids (Hemiptera: Aphididae). *Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society*, 93(4), 313-326.
- Hassan, M. W. U., Nadeem, M., Rehman, H. U., Iqbal, J., Hanif, M. S., Rasool, A., ... & Haque, E. U. (2023). Biophysical Management of Aphid (*Schizaphis graminum* Rondani)(Hemiptera: Aphididae) in Wheat Crop. *Journal of Applied Research in Plant Sciences*, 4(01), 477-484.
- Hodek, I. (1967). Bionomics and ecology of predaceous Coccinellidae. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 12, 79-104.
- Holling, C. S. (1959). Some characteristics of simple types of predations and parasitism. *The Canadian Entomologist*, 91(7), 385-398.
- Honek, A., Martinkova, Z., Kindlmann, P., Ameixa, M. C., & Dixon, A. F. G. (2013). Long-term trends in the composition of aphidophagous coccinellid communities in Central Europe. *Insect Conservation and Diversity*, 7, 55-63.
- Khan, H. A. A., Akram, W., Iqbal, J., & Naeem-Ullah, U. (2015). Thiamethoxam resistance in the house fly, *Musca domestica* L.: current status, resistance selection, cross-resistance potential and possible biochemical mechanisms. *Plos One*, 10, 10-18.
- Khan, H. A., & Suhail, A. (2001). Feeding efficacy, circadian rhythms and oviposition of the lady bird beetle (Coccinellidae: Coleoptera) under controlled conditions. *International Journal of Agriculture & Biology*, 384-386.
- Khan, I., Din, S., Khalil, S. K., Rafi, M. A. (2007): Survey of predatory Coccinellids (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) in the Chitral district, Pakistan. *Journal of Insect Science* 7(7), 1-6.
- Khan, M. H., & Yoldaş, Z. (2018). Assessment of the functional response parameters of *Coccinella septempunctata* to varying densities of *Acyrtosiphon pisum*. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Entomology*, 21(4), 1165-1170.
- Marri, A. H., Majeedano, A. Q., Mari, J. M., Jiskani, A. M., Laghari, M. A., Rustamani, F. A., & Samoo, Y. (2021). Feeding potential of *Coccinella septempunctata* (L.) on mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kaltenbach) and Akk aphid, *Aphis nerii* (Boyer de Fonscolombe). *Journal of Entomological Research*, 45(4), 636-640.

- Marshall, S., (2001) Ontario Lady Beetles (On-line). <http://animal-diversity.ummz.umich.edu/local/.php/http://www.uguelph.ca/~samarsha/lady-beetles.htm>. Accessed 03 March 2022.
- Mayo, A., (1998). Nature Notes - The Ladybug" (On-line). <http://animaldiversity.ummz.umich.edu/local/redirect.php/http://wncnaturecenter.org/natnotes/ladybug.html>. Accessed 03 March 2022.
- Messelink, G. J., Bloemhard, C. M., Sabelis, M. W., & Janssen, A. (2013). Biological control of aphids in the presence of thrips and their enemies. *Bio Control*, 58, 45-55.
- Michaud, J. P. (2012). Coccinellids in biological control. In Hodek I., van Emden H. F. & Honek A. (eds): Ecology and Behaviour of the Ladybird Beetles (Coccinellidae). *John Wiley & Sons, Chichester*, pp. 488-519.
- Mills, N. J. (1982). Satiation and the functional response: a test of a new model. *Ecological Entomology*, 7(3), 305-315.
- Mushtaq, S., Rana, S. A., Khan, H. A., & Ashfaq, M. (2013). Diversity and abundance of family Aphididae from selected crops of Faisalabad, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 50, 103-109.
- Nizamani, M. H., Abro, M. A., Gadhi, M. A., Keerio, A. U., Talpur, M. S. A., & Qazi, S. (2020). Evaluation of different essential oils and bio control agents against *Alternaria alternata* the causal agent of fruit rot of jujube. *Journal of Applied Research in Plant Sciences*, 1(1), 1-8.
- Omkar, & Srivastava, S. (2003). Functional response of the seven spotted lady beetle, *Coccinella septempunctata* Linnaeus on the mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kaltenbach). *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*, 23(2), 149-152.
- Omkar, P. A., Mishra, G., Srivastava, S., Singh, S. K., & Gupta, A. K. (2005). Intrinsic advantages of a ladybird, *Cheilomenes sexmaculata*, over the relatively bigger two co-occurring *Coccinella* species. *Insect Science*, 12, 179-184.
- Pervez, A., & Omkar (2005). Functional responses of coccinellid predators: an illustration of a logistic approach. *Journal of Insect Science*, 5(1), 5-13.
- Raboudi, F., Ben Moussa, A., Makni, H., Marrakchi, M., & Makni, M. (2002). Serological detection of plant viruses in their aphid vectors and host plants in Tunisia. *EPPO Bulletin*, 32(3), 495-498.
- Sattar, M., Ahmed, M., & Nadeem, S. (2008). Biology of *Coccinella septempunctata* Linn. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) and its predatory potential on cotton aphids, *Aphis gossypii* Glover (Hemiptera: Aphididae). *Pakistan Journal of Zoology*, 40(4), 239-242.
- Sepe, M., Daud, I. D., & Gassa, A. (2020). Infectivity of *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo) against *Tribolium castaneum* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). *Journal of Applied Research in Plant Sciences*, 1(2), 53-58.
- Skouras, P. J., Stathas, G. J., Voudouris, C. C., Darras, A. I., Tsitsipis, J. A., & Margaritopoulos, J. T. (2017). Effect of synthetic insecticides on the larvae of *Coccinella septempunctata* from Greek populations. *Phytoparasitica*, 45(2), 165-173.
- Slipinski, A. (2013). Australian ladybird beetles (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae): their biology and classification. CSIRO publishing. pp. 288.
- Solangi, B. K. (2004). Biological control through natural enemies. Model Farming, Pakissan.com. pp. 1-5.
- Soni, R., Deol, G. S., & Singh, S. (2013). Seasonal dynamics of wheat aphid complex and predator *Coccinella septempunctata* in relation to abiotic and biotic factors. *Journal of Environmental Biology*, 34(4), 689-694.
- Srivastava, S., & Omkar. (2003). Scanning electron microscopy of antennae of *Coccinella septempunctata* (Coccinellidae: Coleoptera). *Insect Science*, 10(4), 271-279.
- Uygun, N., & Karabuyuk, F. (2013), Coccinellidae (Gelin Bocekleri). <http://www.biyolojikmucadele.org.tr/uploads/Coccinellidae.pdf>. Data accessed: June 2022.
- Veeravel, R., & Baskaran, P. (1997). Functional and numerical Responses of *Coccinella transversalis* Fab. and *Cheilomenes sexmaculatus* Fab. feeding on the Melon Aphid, *Aphis gossypii* Glov. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*, 17(3-4), 335-339.
- Xia, J. Y., Rabbinge, R., & Van Der Werf, W. (2003). Multistage functional responses in a ladybeetle-aphid system: scaling up from the laboratory to the field. *Environmental Entomology*, 32(1), 151-162.
- Xue, Y., Bahlai, C. A., Frewin, A., Sears, M. K., Schaafsma, A. W., & Hallett, R. H. (2009). Predation by *Coccinella septempunctata* and *Harmonia axyridis* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) on *Aphis glycines* (Homoptera: Aphididae). *Environmental Entomology*, 38(3), 708-714.
- Yu, C., Lin, R., Fu, M., Zhou, Y., Zong, F., Jiang, H., Lv, N., Piao, X., Zhang, J., Liu, Y., & Brock, T. C. M. (2014). Impact of imidacloprid on life-cycle development of *Coccinella septempunctata* in laboratory microcosms. *Journal of Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*, 110, 168-173.